

Does Organizational Change Promote Job Satisfaction of Police Officials in Pakistan? A Quantitative Analysis

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Abstract

Organizational change is considered ideal to produce unexpected events. Hence, the purpose of this study is to find out the influence of organizational change on employees' job satisfaction. It also aims to examine the mediating role of perceived stress and psychological uncertainty within the relationship between organizational change towards job satisfaction. The data were collected from 342 police officials of district Rawalpindi working in twenty-nine police stations of eleven circles. Demographics, Validity and Correlation analysis were performed. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used for hypothesis testing in the present study. Organizational change was observed to be positively related to the job satisfaction of employees. Moreover, perceived stress and psychological uncertainty were witnessed to be playing a mediating role between organizational change and job satisfaction. This particular research work is considered as one of the first efforts towards examination of organizational change and job satisfaction of police officials along with mediations i.e., perceived stress and psychological uncertainty.

Key Words: Organizational Change, Perceived Stress, Psychological Uncertainty, Job Satisfaction, Police Officials.

1. Introduction

Organizational change is capable to produce unplanned consequences. It has been pointed out by the researchers that perceived stress, emotional exhaustion and psychological uncertainty produce lower job satisfaction, increase turnover rates (Bernerth et al., 2011; De Vries, 2013), decrease job performance, and increase absenteeism (Wynen, Verhoest, & Kleizen, 2019). The ability of enterprises to be open to change has become vital in the modern changing era. However, the future is uncertain often in terms of change; in general, the workforce is not motivated toward change unless there are necessary convincing reasons to do so. Moreover, a key issue in planning and managing change projects successfully is creating a basis that supports change. As well as after the implementation of the change process there are some considerable consequences such as the satisfaction of employees. Many of the change processes produce perceived stress and psychological uncertainty among employees (Wisse & Sleebos, 2016), which may affect their level of job satisfaction.

On implementing the change process the stress increases, which produces supplementary demands that usually needed to be met by available resources (Smollan, 2015). However, there

are different levels of stress, that individuals experience because of change. Definitely, in disparity with the general belief that employees are horizontal to act in response towards change in a reliable way, research indicates that employees' level of change-related distress varies according to the change confrontation (Bareil, Savoie, & Meunier, 2007).

Organizational change may be associated with increased occupational demands (i.e., the time demands and magnitude of work) and a shrinking of occupational control (i.e., authority over decisions regarding clients, co-workers and one's tasks). Prior research has linked the extent, to which individuals are involved in the whole change process, such as employee participation in organizing, controlling, planning, leading and implementing changes, with a higher level of control as well as a lower level of psychological uncertainty (Bordia et al., 2004). Organizational change redesigns the framework of organizational structure in terms of group boundaries, reporting hierarchy, interpersonal relationships as well as social identities associated with group memberships and the status of the workforce.

However, if the change is implemented for constructive reasons (e.g. to remain competitive and adjust to changing conditions), the workforce often responds negatively in direction of change and opposes change efforts (Jones et al., 2008). This particular negative reaction is because the change brings uncertainty, stress and increased pressure for employees. Changing environmental demands for markets require organizations to adapt to the change rapidly and accordingly. The higher level of emotional intelligence facilitates to mitigation of the effects of uncertainty and change, furthermore improves employee outcomes such as job satisfaction and performance (King, 2020).

The literature on the management of organizational change has uncovered the prominent role of change receivers to authorize their reactions in support of workplace uncertainty. However, there is an essential need for further research on the influential character of change-related uncertainty and workforce adaptability to understand organizational actions. In the study of Roemer, Sutton and Medvedev (2021), the relationship between organizational change and job satisfaction was examined. Moreover, the impact of organizational change on job satisfaction was found by Hayajneh et al. (2021). In addition to that the association between organizational change and job satisfaction was observed in the previous study (Drosos et al., 2021). In these research studies the mediating role of perceived stress and psychological uncertainty was overlooked. Hence, the present study was carried out to fill out the literature gap. Based on the social exchange theory, the contemporary research study believes in the mutual gains perspective, and it hypothesizes that organizational change is a means for promoting employee job satisfaction because the key imperative of exchange and reciprocity (Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005). As a result, employees will view organizational change as an indication that their employers care about them and will reciprocate by having better attitudes (i.e. a high level of job satisfaction) (Dorta-Afonso, Romero-Domínguez & Benítez-Núñez, 2023).

Drosos et al., (2021) also explained that the particular research they had carried out has provided a theoretical investigation on the connection between employee job satisfaction and change management. Later studies could address the problem of job satisfaction and managing change explains different cases in order to point out other possible differences (Hayajneh et al., 2021). Therefore, this research study has analyzed the mediating role of psychological uncertainty and perceived stress within the relationship between organizational change and employees' job satisfaction. Moreover, carrying out research in different nations would be useful; in this regard, it would be probable to recognize the different observations that exist and to see how different dynamics and situations affect its existence and the extent of the issue of organizational change and job satisfaction (Roemer, Sutton, & Medvedev, 2021).

According to the Annual Administration Report 2010-11, the Punjab Police department has started new systems to change the police culture as well as increase efficiency and effectiveness. These systems were the Police Record & Office Management Information System, Pakistan Automated Finger Print Identification System, Punjab Police Web site, Posting Record System, Daily Crime Report System in Investigation Branch, Initiative to Improve Traffic Management, Computerization of Counter Terrorism Department, E-Policing in Punjab Highway Patrol and Management of E-Complaints. However, there was a need for computer/ information technology training for them, which was organized by the department. There are essentially two types of dimensions in police reforms (Taimur, 2021). First focuses on internal changes, which affect the performance, transparency and efficiency of the system. The second one covers expectations regarding accountability and public service delivery (Abbas, 2011). Traditional police officials are facing problems like if the data entry operator is not available so how to write the FIR because they do not know about local language typing. Some of the traditional police officials were not well known about information technology so they are facing the impacts of change in police reforms and their job satisfaction is going to hurt because of stress and uncertainty. Hence, the purpose of the contemporary research study is to find out the relationship between organizational change and job satisfaction. It also aims to investigate the mediating mechanism of psychological uncertainty and perceived stress in the aforementioned relationship.

2. Theory and Hypothesis Development

2.1 Organizational Change and Job Satisfaction

It is a systematic approach to dealing with the transformation or transition of an organization's processes, technologies or goals. The function of organizational change is to implement strategies for effecting change, helping people to adapt to change and controlling change (Joshi, 2021). The key purpose of organizational changes pertaining to the proposition i.e., to advance the vision and mission so as to adjust with global variations (Castillo, Fernandez, & Sallan, 2018). Contemporary organizations are continuously struggling for the development and application of different types of changes for quick responses towards the rapid expansions pertaining to the external environment, which may cause owing to political, economic, technological and social forces). Therefore, organizations ought to react efficiently to these confront as well as take opportunities as an advantage (Abu Zayyad et al., 2021; Heckelman, 2017). Performance improvement is also a proposed expectation of organizational change (Schneider, Brief, & Guzzo, 1996). There are different forms of coming changes. However, some of the changes have a whole impact on the organizations, on the other hand, some only put effect on certain processes, teams and departments (Yousef, 2017).

Both unexpected and expected pressures (internal and external) may force the organization to take necessary corrective measures, such as approaches, culture, policies, strategies and restructuring to support sustainability and attainment of competitive advantages (Shah, Irani, & Sharif, 2017; Alshurideh, 2010). The basic requirement of successful organizational change is acceptance from the employees (Fairbrother & Warn, 2003). The attitudes of the workforce are influenced by understanding the conditions changing as well as the impact level on them (Cullen et al., 2014). Many of the employees are not motivated to feel satisfied and are not rich with experience to cope with the organizational change, being a major cause of change obstruction or resistance (Alshurideh, Nicholson, & Xiao, 2012). To remain strong in the environment organizations need to develop valuable and effective change methods and strategies (Salloum, Alshurideh, & Al Kurdi, 2019). Contemporary researchers are in

agreement that effective and proper communication being the most efficient strategy towards the enhancement of employee temperament pertaining to acceptance which is imperative because the employees being a critical and participative role in the organizational change process (Petrou, Demerouti, & Schaufeli, 2018).

During organizational change, the quality of communication depends upon the organizational capability and capacity to provide relevant, valuable and timely information to persist consistently (Demerouti, & Schaufeli, 2018; Wanberg & Banas, 2000). The variations or changes become more entrenching, when three stages or levels inside an organization or firm (i.e., organizational, cluster and individual) work together and cohesively (Heckelman, 2017). Organizational variation or change is all about a series of exertions or efforts towards bringing valuable variation or change in the processes, technology, structures and goals of the organization (Carnall, 1986; Yousef, 2000; Yousef, 2017). Golembiewski (1995) explained that organizational change is a transitional process between the future-focused or targeted scenario and the current situation. Usually, a typical daily routine process of work life, is within the outline of processes, for instance, salary freezes, relocations and mergers (Castillo, Fernandez, & Sallan, 2018). Seo et al., (2012) assessed the organizational variation or change via three temperaments or dimensions, namely, creative behavior for change or variation, behavioral facilitation or support for change and behavioral resistance to change or variation. Nevertheless, Dahl (2011) used six dimensions for the measurement of organizational change: increased coordination, cooperation, adaption to turbulent environments, increased effectiveness and enhanced skills and knowledge in the organization (Khan et al., 2018). Whereas, leadership is radically related towards the change process dimensions owing to its character or role of proficiently or efficiently relaying with the workforce as well as providing rewards (Khan et al., 2018). Keeping this in view it can be hypothesized:

H₁: Organizational change is directly related with the job satisfaction of employees.

2.2 Perceived Stress and Organizational Change

It is an employee's assessment of the level of hazard or threat from the employer or stressors, as well as their capacity to survive along with the threat (Liu, et al., 2021). According to Selye (1936), stress is the vague response of the human body to any requirement ready on it. He also described the circumstances manifested by a particular syndrome, which has consisted of all unspecific stimulate changes within the human's biological system (Selye, 1956). Lazarus (1966) explained the concept of the cognitive appraisal system as according to the stress is the outcome of inequality among the demands placed on employees and their internal resources to accomplish those particular demands (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Stress has perceived incongruity, due to inadequate dealing with the stressors, and has adverse physical and mental health-related impacts (Arnold, Cooper, & Robertson, 1998). The researchers have investigated the characteristics of "person-environment interaction" considerably when the psychological progression throughout which it occurs (Dewe, 1992).

Consequently, the modern stance guides the researchers to deem stress as the effect of a "transaction" among individuals and their environment. The expression "transaction" explains stress is neither in an environment nor in the workforce. However, it is an interconnection between them (Lazarus, 1990). Stress has increased when an employee perceives the requirement for fastidious transactions as more than available resources in an organization (Lazarus, 1991). Moreover, the stress begins when the stressor goes beyond the employee's coping up capacity. Nonetheless, perceived stress is a general assessment of workers' stress

and is the scope to which humans find their lives overloading, unpredictable and uncontrollable (Cohen, Kamarck, & Mermelstein, 1983). The perceived stress factor has related with methodological deficiencies between the knowledge deliverer and knowledge taker (Contreras et al., 2021). The significant factors of perceived stress are financial problems, lack of safety and practical attachments (Worku et al., 2020). According to the above-explained literature, it can be hypothesized:

H₂: Organizational change is directly related to perceived stress among employees.

2.3 Psychological Uncertainty and Organizational Change

It is a situation, in which there is not enough knowledge about the magnitude, probability and consequences of events. It is difficult to make correct decisions when there is a high degree of psychological uncertainty in the workforce (Sias & Wyers, 2001). According to the employee perspective, organizational change entails the application of measures causing insecurity, instability and disruption. The employees have not always been provided with autonomy, respect and adequate information. Consequently, the workforce is not capable to understand change benefits and they feel unable to look after their own work interests, which produces psychological uncertainty in them (Bordia et al., 2004). Psychological uncertainty in the direction of organizational change has a considerably unenthusiastic influence on organizational citizenship behavior and psychological capital (Rettie & Daniels, 2021). In the case of the evolution of organizational change, the workforce experience anxiety and uncertainty feelings, and fear arise that in the post-change organizational environment, they will practice role overload or role conflict, or have inferior status, reduced remuneration, or less job security. These uncertainties or fears can trim down their collective trust or identification psychologically (Hui & Lee, 2000).

Psychological uncertainty produces stress headed for organizational change (Robbins & Judge, 2011). This role stress has been categorized into three sub-variables: role overload, role conflict and role ambiguity. Role overload produces if an employee does not have the personal capability of their role fulfilment. Role conflict explains that an employee is unable in dealing with problems. Role ambiguity is a situation where an employee has insufficient information, these situations generates psychological uncertainty (Allen et al., 2007). When the organization is facing psychological uncertainty towards organizational change, it should ascertain a leadership group comprising people who are trusted by the workforce and have well-built interpersonal relationships. This group can assist the workforce in participating and understanding the change, as well as generating more optimistic attitudes (Wisse & Sleebos, 2016). Hence, it is hypothesized that:

H₃: Organizational change has a significant impact on the psychological uncertainty of employees.

2.4 Job Satisfaction, Perceived Stress and Psychological Uncertainty

Job satisfaction is the level of gratification, that employees feel with their job. This goes beyond their daily duties to cover satisfaction with team members and managers, satisfaction with organizational policies, and the impact of their job on employees' personal lives (NGUYEN, NGUYEN, & Thanh LE, 2021). According to Abekah-Nkrumah and Atinga (2013), job satisfaction affects work outcomes and employees' behaviour. Some studies have indicated that job satisfaction has a considerable effect on the work outcomes and attitudes of employees (Suifan, Diab, & Abdallah, 2017). Some researchers have agreed on the point that employee

satisfaction is an important factor for workforce loyalty and productivity (Amin, Aldakhil, Wu, Rezaei, & Cobanoglu, 2017). Naturally, positive and satisfied employees produce consumer satisfaction, and the consequence is high financial performance (Ghannajeh, et al., 2015; Sarraf, 2018). According to Ahmad, Jasimuddin and Kee (2018), job satisfaction has considered a measure of the degree to which the workforce has negative and positive feelings towards the external or internal aspects of related jobs. However, Job satisfaction is an amalgamation of evaluative sensation, which the workforce feel about the work environment (Sarraf, 2018).

Job satisfaction is the emotion, which determines whether to seek another job or remain in the organization. It is a valuable challenge to measure job satisfaction for both managers and researchers (Haque et al., 2012; Masa'deh, 2016), also explained job satisfaction in the dimensions of organizational and personal factors. The first dimension includes race, age, gender and religion, whereas organizational factors are technology innovation, organizational culture and leadership. Al-Abdullat & Dababneh (2018) considered several dimensions of job satisfaction such as counterproductive behavior, turnover, absenteeism, performance & productivity, physical & mental illness, stress, self-esteem and overall life satisfaction. Hayes, Douglas and Bonner (2015) presented six dimensions of job satisfaction such as professional status, interaction, organizational policies, task requirements, autonomy and pay. Some researchers also have measured job satisfaction by using its two dimensions like extrinsic and intrinsic job satisfaction (Tsounis & Sarafis, 2018; Tarcan et al., 2017), as they have been considered to be reliable and valid. Masa'deh (2016) also explained job satisfaction factors, which has related to environmental aspects of the job such as pay, coworkers and working conditions. Extrinsic job satisfaction includes the ingredients related to working conditions, leadership & management techniques, colleagues, human relations, wages, occupational progression, company policies & practices and insurance coverage (Tarcan et al., 2017). In view of the above-explained literature following hypotheses can be developed.

H₄: Perceived stress is positively related with job satisfaction.

H₅: Psychological uncertainty positively relates with job satisfaction.

2. 5 Proposed Research Framework and Hypothesis

This particular proposed research framework was built on the foundation of previous literature. The proposed theoretical model has been presented in Figure 1. Organizational change is independent and job satisfaction is the dependent variable, whereas perceived stress and psychological uncertainty are mediating variables. The following hypotheses about mediation can be developed from the framework:

H₆: Perceived stress mediates the relationship between organizational change and job satisfaction.

H₇: Psychological uncertainty mediates the relationship between organizational change and job satisfaction

Figure 1. Conceptual Model of the Study

3. Methodology

3.1 Participants and Data Collection

The participants in this particular study were police officials (sub-inspectors) of the district Rawalpindi of Punjab. Sub-Inspectors have been selected for this study because they are key investigators in the department as well as at some places they are engaged in working as Station House Officers and In-charges of Police Posts. According to the official website of Punjab Police (<https://www.punjabpolice.gov.pk/RawalpindiDirectory>), there are eleven circles of police in the district of Rawalpindi. Due to the secrecy of the department, the number of sub-inspectors has not been disclosed as the approximate number has been calculated. Whereas approximately there are 955 sub-inspectors, working in district Rawalpindi at police stations. Almost 45 percent of sub-inspectors were engaged in their service before the change (having 15 or more years' service in their credit); selected because they served in both situations before the change and after the change, it may be easy for them to fill up the questionnaire. However, the sample size is 430, which is 45 percent of 955. Therefore, the quota sampling technique was used.

The self-report questionnaires (survey packets) were given on "Front Desks" in separate envelopes on a personal visit to all 29 police stations. The first page of the instrument outlined the survey's voluntary nature, assurance of confidentiality and objectives of the study. On the second page, instructions were written that after filling out give back these forms to the front desk in the envelope, which has been attached to the questionnaire.

3.2 Measures

3.2.1 Organizational change

It was measured using Bouckennooghe, Devos and Broeck (2009) organizational change scale. It includes fifty-three items, measuring three main dimensions of organizational change: Process of Change, Climate of Change or Internal Context, and Readiness for Change. Four sub-dimensions of the "Process of change" are quality of change communication, participation, the attitude of top management toward change and support by supervisors.

Three sub-dimensions of “Climate of Change or Internal Context” are trust in leadership, politicking and cohesion.

In addition, three sub-dimensions of “Readiness for change” are emotional readiness for change, cognitive readiness for change and intentional readiness for change.

Example items are “Information provided on change is clear”, “It is difficult to ask help from my colleagues” and “The change will simplify work”.

3.2.2 Perceived stress

It was measured using the twelve-item scale developed by Cohen, Kamarck and Mermelstein (1983). It consists of two major dimensions of perceived stress including feelings and thoughts of employees during the last month.

Example items are “In the last month have you felt nervous and stressed?” and “In the last month have you been able to control irritations in life?”

3.2.3 Psychological uncertainty

It was assessed using Rafferty and Griffin (2006) four-item version of the psychological uncertainty scale, consisting of four items.

Example items are “My work environment is changing in an unpredictable manner” and “I am often unsure how severely a change will affect my work unit”.

3.2.4 Job Satisfaction

It was measured using Macdonald and MacIntyre (1997) job satisfaction scale, which includes ten items.

Example items are “I receive recognition for a job well done” and “I get along with my supervisors”. The dimensions including recognition, bonding, security health and compensation have been used as the indicators for job satisfaction.

The entire items were being measured accordingly on a five-point Likert scale i.e., one being (strongly agree) and upto five being (strongly disagree).

4. Results

4.1 Common Method Bias Analysis

As this study uses cross-sectional data common method bias analysis was also done. First, Harman's single-factor technique showed that 41.2% of the variance could be explained by just one factor. Thus, common method bias does not appear to be a concern. A study of common latent factors was then performed. Between .00 and .06, the delta for the factor loadings in the retained measurement model with a common latent factor did not significantly differ from those in the retained measurement model without the common latent factor. These findings show that our data are not significantly affected by common technique variance.

4.2 Demographics Analysis

In this study, 400 questionnaires were distributed among the respondents, and 319 filled and utilizable questionnaires were returned, presenting a response rate of 79%. Table 1 presents the respondent demographics for example age, working experience, education level, and qualification.

Personally administered the distribution of 430 questionnaires pertaining to respondents, 350 filled forms were received back whereas 342 of them were properly filled, representing a response rate of 80%. Table 1 is presenting the demographics of the respondents such as age, gender and qualifications.

Table. 1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Demographic	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	40-50	158	46.2
	50-60	184	53.8
Gender	Male	315	92.1
	Female	27	7.9
Qualification	Matric	138	40.4
	Intermediate	102	29.8
	Bachelor	68	19.9
	Masters	34	9.9

4.2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

CFA was performed in AMOS-18 for validity analysis. Since AVE were above 0.50 and AVE > MSV for all variables, thus indicating that all the items were acceptable.

4.3 Correlation Analysis

The values of Means, Standard Deviations, and Correlations among study variables are exhibited in table 3. The results showed that organizational change was positively correlated with job satisfaction where $r = 0.601$ at $p < 0.01$, with perceived stress $r = 0.499$ at $p < 0.01$ and psychological uncertainty $r = 0.184$ at $p < 0.01$. According to the results perceived stress was observed as positively correlated with job satisfaction where $r = 0.716$ at $p < 0.01$ as well as the correlation of psychological uncertainty and job satisfaction $r = 0.536$ at $p < 0.01$, whereas perceived stress and psychological uncertainty $r = 0.876$ at $p < 0.01$.

Table 2. Mean, Standard Deviation and Correlations

		Mean	SD	OC	PS	PU	JS
OC	Organizational Change	2.9004	.39260	1			
PS	Perceived Stress	3.3411	.63455	.499**	1		
PU	Psychological Uncertainty	3.4773	.72201	.184**	.876**	1	
JS	Job Satisfaction	2.6026	.59393	.601**	.716**	.536**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

4.4 Hypotheses Testing

AMOS 18 software was used to pursue the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) method to test the required hypotheses. The required method has been depicted due to its logical strength and to verify and check the relationship among the concepts along with the items measurement. Two stage model-structure procedure was anticipated to apply this method by research scholars. Measurement of the model was verified for the validation i.e., pertaining to the instrument, and further followed by a detailed examination pertaining to structural model for verification of relations among the conjectured within the prevailing research study framework.

Figure 2. Path Diagram of the constructs of the study through AMOS

According to Figure 2 and Table 3, in hypotheses, this research observed the influence of organizational change on job satisfaction. The result showed that organizational change was observed to have a positive influence on job satisfaction ($\beta=0.29$).

Furthermore, organizational change was established to be significant for perceived stress ($\beta=0.50$), supporting H2. In addition, the organizational change was observed to have positive impact on psychological uncertainty ($\beta=0.18$) supporting H3. Moreover, perceived stress was found to positively influencing job satisfaction ($\beta=0.60$) supporting hypothesis H4. However, psychological uncertainty was not significantly related with job satisfaction ($\beta= -0.06$) wherein no support was observed for H5.

For mediation analysis, the main model was divided into three sub-models. In the first model, the direct relationship between organizational change and the job satisfaction of employees was tested. In the second model, perceived stress (mediating variable) was tested to examine the direct and indirect relation and in the third model, psychological uncertainty (mediating variable) was analyzed to examine the direct and indirect relationship between independent and dependent variables.

Table 3. Regression Weights of the Constructs

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	p	Label
PS	<---	OC	.499	.076	10.633	***	Accepted
PU	<---	OC	.184	.098	3.465	***	Accepted
JS	<---	OC	.293	.061	7.487	***	Accepted
JS	<---	PS	.605	.037	15.661	***	Accepted
JS	<---	PU	-.065	.029	-1.901	.057	Rejected

Figure 3. Path Diagram showing direct relationship of organizational and job satisfaction

Table. 4 Regression Weights of job satisfaction and organizational change

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	p	Label
JS	<---	OC	.601	.065	13.902	***	Accepted

To check the mediation effect of perceived stress, we first checked the direct relationship of organizational change on job satisfaction as shown in figure 3, the results found significant and positive relationship ($\beta=.59, p<0.05$).

Figure 4. Path Diagram showing mediation effect of perceived stress.

Table. 5 Regression Weights with mediation of perceived stress

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	p	Label
PS	<---	OC	.499	.076	10.633	***	Supported
JS	<---	OC	.325	.060	8.143	***	Supported
JS	<---	PS	.554	.037	13.900	***	Supported

Figure 4 and table 4 reveal that after introducing the third variable perceived stress, the value of β is reduced as .32, which shows partial mediation. Hence, hypothesis 6 is accepted.

Figure 5. Path Diagram showing mediation effect of psychological uncertainty.

Table. 6 Regression Weights with mediation of psychological uncertainty

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	p	Label
PU	<---	OC	.184	.098	3.465	***	Supported
JS	<---	OC	.520	.056	14.058	***	Supported
JS	<---	PU	.440	.030	11.888	***	Supported

Similarly, by adding psychological uncertainty, the value of β is reduced to 0.52 as shown in fig 5 and table 5, hence hypothesis 7 is also supported that psychological uncertainty mediates the relation between organizational change and job satisfaction.

5. Discussion

This particular research was based on a theoretical model to ensure the linkages between organizational change, perceived stress, psychological uncertainty and job satisfaction among employees. The findings demonstrated that organizational change positively influences job satisfaction though some of the literature exhibits that job satisfaction was negatively influenced by organizational change (Alshurideh, Nicholson, & Xiao, 2012). In previous studies, the relationship between job satisfaction and organizational change was measured (Hayajneh et al., 2021; Drosos et al., 2021; Roemer, Sutton, & Medvedev, 2021), and they recommended that in future the research should be carried out with different mediations i.e. perceived stress and psychological uncertainty. The outcomes of this particular work have filled the gap such as exploring the role of perceived stress and psychological uncertainty between organizational change and job satisfaction of the workforce.

This work is all about after organisational change the situations were arised in Rawalpindi Police Department from their employees' point of view. Its major concern was to dig out the

hypothetical relations between organizational change with perceived stress and psychological uncertainty as well as the connection of job satisfaction after the organizational change. However, there were positive associations between organizational change and perceived stress as well as organizational change and psychological uncertainty discovered. Moreover, another positive association was between perceived stress and job satisfaction, on the other hand, there was a negative association between psychological uncertainty and job satisfaction and the hypothesis was rejected; which presents that after the organizational change, psychological uncertainty was created, and due to this uncertainty: their job satisfaction level was decreased.

Both the mediating variables i.e. perceived stress and psychological uncertainty were strongly mediating the association of organizational change and job satisfaction, which presents that the change produces stress and uncertainty among the workforce. However, in order to avoid the above-said consequences of change; there is a need for valuable measures against after-change shocks in organizations. The results of this particular study are also presenting that the perceived stress produced after the organizational change enhanced the job satisfaction of police officials. Hence, the main fruit of this study is that perceived stress could become a good enabler for job satisfaction, whereas psychological uncertainty should be avoided because of its negative impact on job satisfaction.

5.1 Managerial Implications

Several suggestions are recommended by this research work such as training procedures and teamwork are necessary before the change implementation in organizations. In order to avoid the status quo among police officials, there is a need for both types of training such as training procedures about work coming in future as well as about the fruits of change to avoid psychological uncertainty. According to the results, perceived stress after the organizational change is not disturb job satisfaction among police officials, this presents that it is not a valuable factor to avoid. If the workers are working in teams, maybe all are not stressed about change implementation; as a worker is doing a lot for the team after the change, the other stressed team members may start their work with help. The managers need to know about the problems of their workers arising after the change implementation. Moral support is necessary for any stressed worker from his higher authorities. Because sometimes workers want to work but find it difficult to adopt new procedures, even if they are unfamiliar with work methods. The managers should act like team members for them to avoid psychological uncertainty among them for better organizational development and change adaptation.

5.2 Conclusion

This study was conducted on police officials working in the Rawalpindi District of Punjab. According to this particular work organizational change has a positive impact on job satisfaction because after some time of organizational change, with new less time-consuming procedures of work; most of the workers are feeling satisfied with their work. On the other hand, at the start of organizational change, two emotions may be produced like stress and uncertainty. Both are harmful to the workforce but different in levels such as perceived stress, which may cover with the help of other employees and may not affect job satisfaction. When psychological uncertainty produces, a hazardous situation arises, because according to the results of this study, there is a decrease in job satisfaction among employees, when the psychological uncertainty situation increases.

5.3 Limitations and Future research directions

This research is limited in a number of ways. First, the data was taken from the police officials of a single district. The data could be taken at the provincial level as well as the country level.

However, the data can be taken from other service sectors such as private security companies, which are working almost on the same nature of work. Secondly, the discussed change in this research paper was eleven years ago. Consequently, the data could have been taken from the organizations where changes occur recently such as the KPK police department. Thirdly, the data was taken from a public sector department; it could be taken from private sectors like production and service sectors such as banks, cotton mills, automobile, aviation industry and other SMEs. Moreover, the research is limited in variables; only two mediating variables have been discussed between organizational change and job satisfaction, it is a need for future research to study the relation of other mediating and moderating variables i.e. motivation, agility, and training. However, it is a survey-based study with the self-reported questionnaire, bias may occur, so in future, there is a need for a longitudinal study with an experimental design.

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Appendix**Table. 7 Detail of Participants**

Circles	Police Stations	Approximate Number of Sub-Inspectors
Cantt	R.A Bazar, Westridge, Race Course and Naseerabad	130
Saddar	Saddar Barooni, Chountra and Rawat	100
City	City, Ganjmandi, Pirwadhai and Ratta Amral	140
Taxila	Taxila, Wah Cantt and Wah Saddar	90
Gujar Khan	Gujar Khan, Mandra and Jatli	110
Waris Khan	Waris Khan and Banni	70
Civil lines	Civil Lines, Airport, Morgah, Women	140
Kahuta	Kahuta and Kallar Syedan	65
New Town	New Town and Sadiqabad	70
Murree	Murree	25
Kotli Sattian	Kotli Sattian	15
Total 11	29	955